

CLASSROOM BEHAVIOR OF LEARNERS AND ITS EFFECT TO THEIR ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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Classroom Behavior of Learners and its Effect to their Academic Performance

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess the classroom behavior of grade 4 - 6 learners in Abaga Integrated School. It also sought to determine the effect of learners' classroom behavior to their academic performance. The researcher used descriptive-correlation research design to describe the classroom behavior of learners towards their classmates, classroom activities and teachers and person in authority and its correlation to the academic performance of the learners. Respondents were 44 grade 4 learners, 42 grade 5 learners, and 30 grade 6 learners. Findings revealed that the classroom behavior of the learners towards their classmates were often demonstrated positive behavior and sometimes for the negative behavior. The same findings to the learners' behavior towards their classroom activities and towards their teachers and person in authority. Regression analysis revealed that there was no significant relationship between learners' academic performance and classroom behavior towards classmates, teachers and person in authority. But there was a significant relationship between academic performance and the classroom behavior towards classroom activities. It was further revealed that there was no significant relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and their academic performance. There was also no significant difference in the classroom behavior of the respondents towards classmates and schoolmates, classroom activities, teachers and person in authority when grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of age, sex, and grade level.

Keywords: *classroom behavior, academic performance, classmates, classroom activities, teacher and person in authority*

Introduction

One of the pertinent issues that teachers nowadays deal with is student behavior in the classroom, seen from a worldwide viewpoint. The behaviors of pupils oftentimes result in the creation of a classroom environment not conducive to learning. Children today believe they are unstoppable and can do anything they want without facing consequences. According to House Bill 4907, often known as the "Positive Discipline Act," it encourages positive and non-violent forms of discipline.

Teachers are then finding it difficult to guide and discipline the students. Teachers are greatly troubled by the ban on corporal punishment in schools since students are now aware of the law and state that they will never be subjected to corporal punishment. From the records of the school guidance designate in Abaga Integrated School, there are 14 cases of bullying, 25 cases of absenteeism,

18 cases of fighting, and 7 cases of grave misconduct. This increased the frequency and intensity of classroom behaviors somehow hindered students' and teachers' learning while also decreasing teaching effectiveness and efficiency.

At some point, trying to make things better is challenging for public school teachers. In the Philippines as much as abroad, they must deal with the difficulties of controlling their students' behavior while following the curriculum. In addition, they deal with a lot of challenging circumstances. Students' academic achievement is significantly impacted by their behavior in the classroom.

These days, student behavior in the classroom can take many different forms, depending on the social and cultural setting in which the schools are located. This is because of the many experiences that the students have had throughout their life.

It is critical to recognize the types of student conduct that are most frequently and widely displayed in the classroom. Teachers will be better equipped to develop suitable solutions to these issues if they identify the difficulties early on. The researcher was thus prompted to carry out this study by the occurrence of classroom behavior and its impact on the academic achievement of students in public primary schools. Academic performance is the basis for improving the teaching-learning process. Evaluation of the performance of the pupils is also an indicator of the quality of teaching. The Department of Education monitors pupils' academic performance to find out if pupils have reached the required level of competency (Dulay, 2020).

The way learners behave in a classroom setting could potentially set the tone for the way they perform on an assessment. Abaga Integrated School depicts a typical classroom setting where teachers have varied sets of approaches in managing their respective classes. When the teachers struggle to teach, learners would likely be learning less than of what they should have been. That is to say, effective learning must not take place inside poorly managed classrooms. Marzano (2013) even furthered that if the learners were disorderly and disrespectful and had no clear rules to guide behaviors, chaos would become its norm.

Hence, this study is intended to assess the behavior of learners in Abaga Integrated School. It also sought to determine the effect of learners' classroom behavior to their academic performance. Moreover, the study was conducted on the first quarter of the school year 2023-2024, in Abaga Integrated School, Balo-i East District. Respondents were the selected learners in Abaga Integrated School, from grade 4 to grade 6.

In addition, within the two years of being a public school teacher, the researcher has observed that learners' behaviors differ over time. For her, one method of finding the cause of this transition was to assess the classroom behavior of the learners and study how those behavior affects the academic performance of the learners. This study could help the teachers of Abaga Integrated School to assess and find out the classroom behavior of their learners and to what extent it affects the academic performance of the learners.

Research Questions

This study attempted to assess the classroom behavior of the learners in Abaga Integrated school. It also looked into the effect of the classroom behavior of learners to their academic performance. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex; and
 - 1.3. grade level?
2. What is the level of classroom behavior of learners in terms of;
 - 2.1. behavior towards classmates or schoolmates;
 - 2.2. behavior towards work and activities, and;
 - 2.3. behavior towards teachers and persons in authority?
3. What is the academic performance of the respondents?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the classroom behavior and academic performance of the respondents?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile and academic performance of the respondents?
6. Is there a significant difference in the classroom behavior of the respondents when grouped according to their demographic profile?
7. What action plan on behavioral intervention can be proposed based on the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a descriptive-correlational research design. The study was descriptive since it described the classroom behavior of learners towards their classmates, classroom activities, and teachers and person in authority. Likewise, the learner's demographic profile and their academic performance were discussed. This study also employed correlation research design since it investigated the relationship between classroom behavior and academic performance of the learners.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were the Grade 4 to Grade 6 learners in Abaga Integrated School. The researcher utilized random sampling by arranging the learners' names in all sections in an alphabetical order. All even-numbered learners automatically became the respondents. Out of 232 learners from grade 4 to grade 6, 116 were chosen as respondents presentation of the respondents.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents by Grade Level*

Grade Level	Section	No. of Learners	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
IV	A	30	15	50.00
IV	B	28	14	50.00
IV	C	30	15	50.00
V	A	42	21	50.00
V	B	42	21	50.00
VI	A	30	15	50.00
VI	B	30	15	50.00
TOTAL		232	116	50.00

Instruments

This study utilized an adapted questionnaire in gathering the necessary data. The survey questionnaire was developed by Dulay (2020) in her study about classroom behavior and academic performance of public school pupils. The survey questionnaire had three parts, the first part was composed of 10 questions about the behavior of the learner toward classmates or schoolmates. Part 2 of the survey questionnaire consisted of 10 questions about the behavior of learners towards class work and school activities. The last part had 10 questions about the learner's behavior towards teachers and persons in authority. Items of the questionnaire were transcribed in Filipino version for the respondents' ease of understanding and comprehending every item. This also helped to obtain a reliable data. On the upper part of the survey questionnaire was the socio-demographic of the respondent, age, sex, and grade level. For the academic performance of the learners, which was a secondary instrument, it was obtained from the records of teacher advisers of the respondents.

The survey used four-point likert scale that asked the respondents how often they practiced each statement in the survey questionnaire. For the positive statements, 4 "practiced at all times" were considered as the highest and 1 "not practiced" as the lowest. On the other

hand, the negative statement had a reverse scoring procedure, compared to the positive statements.

Moreover, the researcher made some changes to the adapted questionnaire to make it fit to the respondents. With that, the researcher conducted a pilot test to validate the reliability of the adapted questionnaire after making minor changes. The reliability coefficient of the pilot test was 0.79, which meant the adapted questionnaire was reliable and valid.

Procedure

To obtain pertinent data, letters were sent asking permission to conduct the survey. First, to the Schools Division Superintendent, then to District Supervisor, to the School Principal, to the teachers and lastly, to the Grade 4 to Grade 6 learners who were the respondents of the study.

Upon its approval, the researcher administered the questionnaires to the respondents during their Homeroom and Guidance subject time. The respondents answered the questionnaire with the assistance of the researcher. The respondents were given enough time to answer the questionnaire and it was then retrieved after the respondents were done answering the questionnaire. Assurance was given that the answer would be confidential.

On the other hand, the researcher asked the respective advisers for each grade level for the first quarter grades of the respondents, which served as the learner's academic performance. The data was collected, analyzed, evaluated, and interpreted.

Data Analysis

For the analysis of data, it used tabulated and interpreted to obtain the actual information required. The following statistical techniques were utilized to answer the different problems presented.

For Problems 1 and 3, frequency and percentage were used in describing the demographic profile in terms of age, sex, and grade level and also their academic performance.

For Problem 2, weighted mean was used in describing the level of classroom behavior of the respondents towards their classmates, classroom activities, and teachers and persons in authority.

For Problems 4, 5, and 6, Regression analysis was used to determine the significant relationship between the classroom behavior and academic performance of the learners and the significant relationship between the demographic profile and academic performance of the learners.

Results and Discussion

This section discusses the data that are shown in the tables. The data were analyzed, interpreted, and supported by related literature or studies.

Problem 1: What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, and grade level?

Table 2. Age of the Respondents

Age (in years)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
9	24	21.00%
10	16	14.00%
11	34	29.00%
12	25	22.00%
13	12	10.00%
14-15	5	4.00%
Total	116	100.00

Table 2 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of age, detailing the frequency and percentage of individuals within specific age brackets. It showed that the highest number were coming from age 11 which was 34 or 29% out of the 116 respondents. Followed by the age 12 at 22%. The least number of respondents were from the age bracket of 14 to 15 years old which was only 5 or 4%. The ages 11 and 12 which had the highest number were the average age of learners from grades 4, 5, and 6, who were the respondents in the survey. This implied that the pool of perceptions gathered and processed in this study were perceptions of persons in the early adolescent stage. The adolescence period is particularly hard time for children. They are experiencing all kinds of new changes in their bodies and their feelings. They often feel misunderstood as they are struggling to leave behind their childhood and move to adulthood.

Adolescence is commonly characterized by issues such as rebellious behavior, lying, cheating, school performance problems, negative attitudes, disobedience and disrespect, sibling rivalry, drug and alcohol abuse, pressures from peers, depression, and issues of sexuality. It is the period when many risk behaviors were at their peak (Arnett, 2019). Based on the sex distribution data presented in Table 3, it is evident that the survey had a higher participation of female respondents. The female respondents, totaling 69 out of 116, constituted 59%, while the male respondents accounted for 47, representing 41% of the total. This indicated a 9% higher representation of female participants compared to male participants in the survey.

Table 3. Respondents' Sex Profile

Sex Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Male	47	41.00%
Female	69	59.00%
Total	116	100.00

Understanding the sex distribution was crucial for interpreting the survey results, as it allowed for consideration of potential sex-related influences on the study findings.

Table 4. Respondents' Grade Level

Grade Level	Frequency	Percentage
Grade IV	44	38.00%
Grade V	42	36.00%
Grade VI	30	26.00%
Total	116	100.00

The data in Table 4 provides an outline of the respondents' distribution based on their respective grade levels. Notably, the largest contingent hailed from Grade IV, constituting 44 out of 116 respondents, equivalent to 38%. Following closely were Grade V learners, comprising 42 individuals or 36%. In contrast, the smallest cohort was represented by Grade VI learners, totaling 30 respondents or 26%. This pattern revealed a diminishing trend in cohort survival as grade levels ascended. The observed decrease in the number of learners with each advancing grade level indicated that not all students from the initial cohort had progressed through the educational stages uniformly. Such insights into grade-level distribution were significant, aligning with existing research emphasizing the importance of monitoring and understanding cohort progression to inform educational policies and interventions (Chen, 2018).

Problem 2: What is the level of classroom behavior of the respondents in terms of behavior towards classmates/schoolmates, behavior towards classroom activities, and behavior towards teachers and persons in authority?

Table 5. Learners' Classroom Behavior Towards Classmates/Schoolmates

Classroom Behavior	Weighted Mean	Remarks
CBTC/S1. I demonstrate respectful behavior. (Nagpapakita ako ng magalang na paguugali)	3.46	Often
CBTC/S2. I say "please" and "thank you" before and after the request is being done. (Nagsasabi ako ng "pakiusap" at "salamat" bago at pagkatapos humingi ng hiling.)	3.15	Often
CBTC/S3. I ask apology whenever necessary (Humihingi ako ng paumanhin pag kinakailangan)	3.01	Often
CBTC/S4. I challenged other's mental and physical weaknesses. (Hinahamon ko ang mental at pisikal na kahinaan ng iba.)	3.40	Sometimes
CBTC/S5. I tease classmates, schoolmates and laugh at anybody's wrong answer. (Tinutukso ko ang aking mga klasmeyt at pinagtatawanan ko ang kanilang maling sagot.)	3.54	Never
CBTC/S6. I enjoy fooling / kidding classmates anybody else in the school which cause troubles. (Nasisiyahan akong lokohin / biruin ang mga kaklase at sinuman sa paaralan na nagdudulot ng kaguluhan.)	3.52	Never
CBTC/S7. I initiate verbal/physical fights. (Nagsisimula ako ng verbal/pisikal na away.)	3.42	Sometimes
CBTC/S8. I possess a good relationship with peers. (Mayroon akong magandang relasyon sa aking mga kasamahan.)	3.25	Often
CBTC/S9. I Interrupt or intrude on others (e.g., butts in into conversations or games). (Nakikialam ako o nanghihimasok sa iba (e.g. nanghihimasok sa usapan o laro.)	3.28	Sometimes
CBTC/S10. I keep hands, feet, objects and unkind remarks to myself. (Tinatago ko sa aking sarili ang aking mga hindi magandang pananalita, at kilos.)	3.19	Often
	Average + 3.21	Often
	Average - 3.43	Sometimes

Table 5 shows the respondents' behavior towards classmates/schoolmates. It revealed that learners had positive behavior as evidenced by the average positive statements weighted mean which was equal to

3.21. This meant they often demonstrated respectful behavior, asked apology if needed, said "please" and "thank you" before and after a request, and possessed a good relationship with peers. Respect is one of the values that the school aimed to develop among the pupils as members of a civilized society. This same effort was extended to the pupils to make them capable of interacting with other pupils in school and the community. This asserted that the way students interacted with their peers and fellow students in the classroom reflected their attitudes toward them. These actions could take the shape of establishing friends, exchanging possessions, or relating to one another as classmates.

As for the negative statement, it was revealed that the weighted mean for the negative statements was 3.43. This meant that the learners sometimes manifested negative behavior, such as challenging the mental and physical weakness of others, initiating verbal/physical fights, and interrupting or intruding on other. Delgado's (2021) study found that interruptions, off-task behavior, and disruptive bodily gestures accounted for most student misbehavior. Verbal interruptions (talking, humming, laughing, crying out, whispering, etc.) and off-task behaviors (dozing, daydreaming, sleeping, playing with something, scribbling, physically sitting on the desk or two legs of a chair, throwing paper, etc.) were the most frequent disruptive behaviors.

Considering the overall findings, the study provided a nuanced understanding of learners' behavior towards classmates/schoolmates, encompassing both positive and negative aspects. This comprehensive insight was vital for educators and administrators to implement targeted strategies that reinforced positive behavior and addressed challenges in creating a conducive learning environment.

Table 6. *Learners' Classroom Behavior Towards School Activities*

Classroom Behavior	Weighted Mean	Remarks
<i>BTCA1. I bring complete materials to be used for class activities at all times. (Laging nagdadala ng mga materyales na gagamitin sa mga aktibidad.)</i>	2.88	Often
<i>BTCA2. I recite with my other classmates (Magrecite kasama ang aking ibang kaklase.)</i>	2.59	Often
<i>BTCA3. I don't participate in group activities. (Hindi ako sumasali sa mga pangkatang aktibidad.)</i>	3.31	Sometimes
<i>BTCA4 I get good grades because I have a good skill in making projects. (Nakakakuha ako ng mahusay na marka dahil mayroon akong mahusay na kasanayan sa paggawa ng proyekto.)</i>	3.08	Often
<i>BTCA5: I copy from the work of others. (Kopyahin ang gawa ng iba.)</i>	3.31	Sometimes
<i>BTCA6. I just play around not doing the projects. (Maglaro lang ako na hindi ginagawa ang proyekto.)</i>	3.44	Sometimes
<i>BTCA7. I do not stand up to recite. (Hindi ako tumatayo para mag recite.)</i>	3.40	Sometimes
<i>BTCA 8. I look around for the answer. (Tumingin sa paligid para sa sagot.)</i>	3.47	Sometimes
<i>BTCA9. I Get angry to my teacher for calling me to recite. (Magalit sa aking guro dahil sa pagtawag sakín para mag recite.)</i>	3.53	Never
+Average	2.85	Often
-Average	3.41	Sometimes

Note: 1.00-1.49, Never; 1.50-2.49, Sometimes; 2.50-3.49, Often; 3.50-4.00, Always (For negative statements, the scoring procedure is the reverse)

Table 6 presents the behavior of learners in terms of school activities. It revealed that the learners often brought complete materials to be used for class activities, often recited with their other classmates, and often got good grades because of their good skills in making projects. Also, they sometimes did not participate in group activities, sometimes copied from the work of others, sometimes played around not doing the projects, sometimes did not stand up to recite, sometimes looked around for the answer and never got angry to their teachers for calling them to recite. The average weighted mean for the positive statements was 2.85, which meant that the learners often manifested positive behavior. Additionally, the negative statement had a weighted mean of 3.41, which implied that the learners sometimes manifested negative behavior toward their classroom activities. The manifestation of behavior was partly due to the reality

in the school setting and the true experience of the learners.

In summary, the study offered a thorough comprehension of learners' conduct during school activities, capturing both favorable and unfavorable aspects. This comprehensive understanding was essential for educators and administrators as they devised focused strategies to bolster positive behavior and tackle challenges. Ultimately, these initiatives played a crucial role in fostering a more efficient and positive learning atmosphere for the students.

Table 7. Learners' Classroom Behavior Towards Teachers and Persons in Authority

Behavior	Weighted Mean	Remarks
<i>BTTPA1. I leave the class with teacher's permission. (Umaalis ako ng klase na may pahintulot ng guro.)</i>	3.26	Often
<i>BTTPA2. I exhibit politeness to the teachers and person of authority. (Nagpapakita ako ng pagiging magalang sa mga guro at taong may awtoridad.)</i>	3.52	Often
<i>BTTPA3. I follow classroom rules and teacher's expectations. (Sinusunod ko ang mga tuntunin sa silid-aralan at sa mga inaasahan ng guro.)</i>	3.27	Often
<i>BTTPA4. I listen quietly while teacher explains. (Tahimik akong nakikinig habang nagpapaliwanag ang guro.)</i>	3.34	Often
<i>BTTPA5. I listen when spoken to directly. (Nakikinig ako kapag direktang kinakausap.)</i>	3.22	Often
<i>BTTPA6. I commit habitual absences from the class. (Nakagawian kong lumiban sa klase.)</i>	3.30	Sometimes
<i>BTTPA7. I talk excessively (Masyado akong nagsasalita.)</i>	3.09	Sometimes
<i>BTTPA 8. I actively defy or refuse to comply request or rules. (Hindi ko sinusunod o tumatanggi ako sa kahilingan o mga panuntunan.)</i>	3.3.27	Sometimes
<i>BTTPA9. I report to class/school late. (Late akong pumupunta sa klase/paaralan.)</i>	3.23	Sometimes
<i>BTTPA10. I challenged teachers and school authorities. (Hinahamon ko ang mga guro at awtoridad ng paaralan.)</i>	3.71	Never
+Average	3.22	Often
-Average	3.32	Sometimes

Note: 1.00-1.49, Never; 1.50-2.49, Sometimes; 2.50-3.49, Often; 3.50-4.00, Always (For negative statements, the scoring procedure is the reverse)

Table 7 portrays the behavior of the learners towards teachers and persons in authority. As revealed in the table, the average weighted mean of positive statements, statement 1 to statement 5, was 3.22, which meant that often the learners manifested positive behavior. As for the negative statements, it was revealed that the learners sometimes manifested negative behavior based on its weighted mean of 3.32.

It could be observed from the result that the learners often left the class with the teacher's permission, exhibited politeness to the teachers and persons of authority, followed classroom rules and teacher's expectations, listened quietly while teacher explained and listened when spoken to directly.

All of those mentioned positive statements came out to be often manifested by the learners. For the statement 6 to statement 10, which had a negative statement showed that it was only sometimes manifested by learners. It meant that learners sometimes committed habitual absences from class, talked excessively, actively defied or refused to comply request, reported to class/school late and never challenged teacher and persons in authority.

This aligned with Dulay's (2020) study, which also found that pupils generally exhibited respect towards teachers and authority figures, following rules and guidance. Similarly, both studies indicated occasional instances of negative behavior among the respondents.

These findings had significant implications for fostering positive learning environments. The consistent manifestation of respectful

behavior towards teachers and authority figures suggested a foundation of mutual respect within the school community. Educators could build upon these positive interactions to further enhance the teacher-student relationship. However, the occasional display of negative behaviors underscored the importance of targeted interventions to address specific challenges. Implementing proactive strategies and reinforcing positive conduct could contribute to a more harmonious and productive educational atmosphere. This ultimately benefiting the overall learning experience for both students and educators.

Problem 3: What is the academic performance of the respondents?

Table 8. Respondents' Academic Performance

Grade Scale	Frequency	Percentage
90-100 Outstanding (P)	18	15.00%
85-89 Very Satisfactory (P)	39	34.00%
80-84 Satisfactory(P)	43	37.00%
75-79 Fairly Satisfactory(P)	16	14.00%
Below 75 Did Not Meet Expectations (F)	0	0.00%
Total	116	100.00

The academic performance of the respondents as shown in table 8 revealed that majority fell on the Satisfactory rating which was in the grade scale range of 80-84 with a frequency of 43. The rest of the learners fell on the fairly satisfactory or got a grade scale range of 75-79. This implied that the majority of the respondents had achieved a level of performance that met or exceeded the expected standard. Satisfactory typically implied that the academic performance was at an acceptable or adequate level. Followed by the Very Satisfactory category in which 39 out of 166 or 34% fell on the grade scale range between 85-89. The grade scale range of 90-100 was the third with a frequency of 18 or 15% of 166.

In essence, these academic performance findings provided valuable insights into the alignment of student achievements with the standards set by the DepEd, emphasizing the need for continuous efforts to support learners across different performance levels.

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between the classroom behavior and the academic performance of the respondents?

The results from regression analysis for the significant relationship between the academic performance and classroom behavior of the respondents towards classmates and schoolmates as shown in Table 9 portrayed no significant relationship. Except for item statement 9 which had a p-value of 0.010 (significant). The rest of the item statements had p-values greater than 0.05. It meant that the behavior of the respondents towards their classmates and schoolmates did not influence their academic performance as evidenced by the average p-value of 0.128 which was greater than 0.05. In contrast, the research conducted by Dulay (2020) demonstrated a noteworthy correlation between students' classroom behavior toward their fellow students and their academic achievement.

Table 9. Regression Analysis Results Between the Classroom Behavior Towards Classmates/Schoolmates and the Academic Performance

Classroom Behavior Towards Classmates/Schoolmates	t-value	p-value	Remarks
BPTCS1	-0.338	0.736	Not Significant
BPTCS2	1.885	0.066	Not Significant
BPTCS3	-0.153	0.879	Not Significant
BPTCS4	0.025	0.980	Not Significant
BPTCS5	1.147	0.254	Not Significant
BPTCS6	-0.227	0.821	Not Significant
BPTCS7	0.219	0.827	Not Significant
BPTCS8	-0.030	0.976	Not Significant
BPTCS9	2.621	0.010	Significant
BPTCS10	-1.380	0.170	Not Significant
Over-all		0.128	Not Significant

Note: ANOVA for Regression: $F=1.562$, Significant at 0.01 level, $R^2=.129$

She claimed that because there was a connection between students' behavior in the classroom and how they behaved toward their peers,

teachers needed to keep an eye on these behaviors in order to provide the appropriate assistance.

Table 10 presents the regression analysis examining the relationship between the classroom behavior towards classroom activities and academic performance. The analysis revealed that there was a significant relationship between the classroom behavior towards classroom activities and academic performance. This meant that the classroom behavior towards classroom activities could influence the academic performance of the learners. It could be seen in the table that among the nine (9) statements about learners' classroom behavior towards classroom activities, 6 statements resulted to significant and only 3 statements were not significant. This indicated that the academic performance of pupils was affected by their behavior towards their classwork. If they participated actively in their academic work, they could learn and their performance would improve. If they did not have good and active participation in the lessons, they would not be able to learn their lesson, and so their performance would be low.

Table 10. *Regression Analysis Results Between the Classroom Behavior Towards Classroom Activities and Academic Performance*

Classroom Behavior Towards Classroom Activities	t-value	p-value	Remarks
BPTCA1	2.422	0.017	Significant
BPTCA2	3.721	0.000	Significant
BPTCA3	1.970	0.050	Significant
BPTCA4	3.093	0.003	Significant
BPTCA5	2.118	0.037	Significant
BPTCA6	1.296	0.198	Not Significant
BPTCA7	3.380	0.001	Significant
BPTCA8	1.460	0.147	Not Significant
BPTCA9	1.165	0.247	Not Significant
Over-all		0.001	Significant

Note: ANOVA for Regression: $F=9.979$, Significant at 0.01 level, $R^2=.459$

The relationship between academic and classroom behavior was a long recognized phenomenon. According to a 2019 study by Joffe and Black, out of a sample of 352 secondary school pupils, those who performed poorly academically had much more behavioral, emotional, and social problems. Numerous studies have also hinted that elements of academic intervention programs may also impact the behavioral domain. Additionally, Maganto (2019) found on his study that pupils' academic achievement was significantly influenced by mental ability, distance of school from the residence, socio-economic status, behavior, and work attitudes. This served as a challenge to teachers to continually brace them for the identified and anticipated behaviors that were really apparent at this adolescent stage, especially to these left-behind students.

Table 11. *Regression Analysis Results Between the Classroom Behavior Towards Teachers and Persons in Authority and Academic Performance*

Classroom Behavior Towards Teachers and Persons in Authority	t-value	p-value	Remarks
BPTTPA1	0.288	0.774	Not Significant
BPTTPA2	0.835	0.406	Not Significant
BPTTPA3	0.107	0.915	Not Significant
BPTTPA4	0.456	0.649	Not Significant
BPTTPA5	-0.517	0.606	Not Significant
BPTTPA6	0.471	0.638	Not Significant
BPTTPA7	1.458	0.148	Not Significant
BPTTPA8	-0.015	0.988	Not Significant
BPTTPA9	0.489	0.626	Not Significant
BPTTPA10	0.164	0.870	Not Significant
Over-all		0.870	Not Significant

Note: ANOVA for Regression: $F=0.524$, Significant at 0.01 level, $R^2=.048$

Table 11 displays the results of a regression analysis examining the relationship between the classroom behavior of learners towards the teacher and person with authority and their academic performance. The analysis revealed that none of the predictors significantly influenced academic performance. This implied that the behavior of the learners towards their teachers and person in authority did not influence their academic performance.

In the research study of Melad (2022) underlined that no meaningful correlation was observed between the respondents' classroom behavior toward their instructor and other authoritative figures and their academic achievement. Regarding this, there was no discernible connection between the kids' conduct toward their instructors and other adults in positions of authority and their academic achievement.

Considering the overall results, it became apparent that while classroom behavior towards teachers and persons in authority was an essential aspect of a conducive learning environment, it might not be the sole predictor of academic performance. This comprehensive understanding was crucial for educators and policymakers as they shaped strategies to enhance academic outcomes, emphasizing a holistic perspective on student behavior and its multifaceted influences.

Problem 5: Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile and the academic performance of the respondents?

Table 12 displays the relationship between the demographic profile of the respondents and their academic performance. It revealed that age did not influence the academic performance of the respondents as evidenced by the p-value of 0.643 which was greater than 0.05 level of significance. This implied that age was not a significant predictor of academic performance in this study. On the other hand, it could be observed on the table that the profile sex had a remark significant. This meant that the sex of the respondents significantly influenced their academic performance.

Table 12. *Correlation Between the Demographic Profile and the Academic Performance*

Demographic Profile			Remarks
Age	Pearson Correlation	-0.044	Not significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.643	
	N	116	
Sex	Pearson Correlation	0.212	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.022	
	N	116	
Grade level	Pearson Correlation	0.065	Not Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.486	
	N	116	

It implied further that the grade level did not influence the academic performance of the respondents as evidence by the p-value 0.065 which was greater than 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between the respondents' demographic profile and their academic performance was not rejected.

These findings aligned with those of Esto (2018), emphasizing that demographic factors did not serve as predictors for academic performance. In both studies, academic performance was not positively correlated with demographic profiles, further emphasizing the importance of understanding other influencing factors. Considering the overall results, the intricate interplay between demographic variables and academic outcomes suggested a need for a holistic approach in educational strategies that went beyond demographic considerations.

Problem 6: Is there a significant difference in the classroom behavior of the respondents when grouped according to their demographic profile?

Table 13. *Significant Difference of Classroom Behavior Towards Classmates When Grouped According to Demographic Profile.*

Demographic Profile	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Age	0.876	0.383	Not Significant
Sex	-0.154	0.877	Not Significant
Grade Level	-0.344	0.731	Not Significant

Note: ANOVA for Regression: $F=0.373$, Significant at 0.01 level, $R^2=.010$

Table 13 shows the significant difference in the classroom behavior of the respondents towards classmates and schoolmates when grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of age, sex, and grade level. Findings revealed that there were no significant differences as the p-values were greater than 0.05 level of significance. It implied that no matter if the respondent was younger or older, their behavior would not be influenced by age. In the same manner, sex was not a predictor of behavior towards classmates and schoolmates as the p-value of 0.877 was not significant.

Table 14 reveals the significant difference in the classroom behavior of the respondents towards classroom activities when grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of age, sex, and grade level. Findings revealed that there were no significant differences in terms of age and sex as the p-values were greater than 0.05 level of significance.

Table 14. *Significant Difference of Classroom Behavior Towards Classroom Activities When Grouped According to Demographic Profile*

Demographic Profile	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Age	-1.898	0.060	Not Significant
Sex	0.976	0.331	Not Significant
Grade Level	3.593	0.000	Significant

Note: ANOVA for Regression: $F=5.401$, Significant at 0.01 level, $R^2=.126$

It implied that the age and sex of the respondents did not influence their behavior towards activities. However, the table further revealed the significant influenced of the respondent's grade level on their behavior towards classroom activities. It meant that as the respondent's grade level increased, the more they performed positive behavior towards their classroom activities.

Table 15 shows the significant difference of classroom behavior towards teachers and persons in authority of the respondents when grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of age, sex, and grade level. Findings revealed that neither age, sex nor grade level had influenced the classroom behavior of respondents as evidenced by the p-values greater than 0.05 level of significance.

Table 15. *Significant Difference of Classroom Behavior Towards Teachers and Persons in Authority When Grouped According to Demographic Profile*

Demographic Profile	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Age	-0.044	0.965	Not Significant
Sex	0.795	0.428	Not Significant
Grade Level	0.825	0.411	Not Significant

Note: ANOVA for Regression: $F=0.729$, Significant at 0.01 level, $R^2=.019$

It implied that whether the respondent was young or older, male or female, there was no significant difference in their classroom behavior towards teachers and other persons in authority. The same was true with grade level, there was no significant difference of the respondent's classroom behavior whether they were in grade IV, V, or grade VI.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, several conclusions were drawn regarding learner behavior and academic performance. Learners exhibited a mix of positive and occasional negative behavior towards their classmates, classroom activities, and teachers. Despite this variability, the majority of students demonstrated a satisfactory level of academic achievement, meeting or exceeding the expected performance standards. Regression analysis showed no significant correlation between classroom behavior towards peers and academic performance. However, there was a notable association between conduct towards classroom activities and academic performance, although other behavioral variables did not significantly impact academic outcomes. Additionally, the demographic profile of students, including age, sex, and grade level, did not significantly affect their academic performance or classroom behavior.

The study highlighted the importance of understanding learner behavior in Grades 4, 5, and 6 and its impact on academic performance. Identifying frequently displayed behaviors in the classroom is crucial for teachers to address issues effectively. Poorly managed classrooms can hinder learning, indicating that effective teaching requires a well-managed environment. The study underscores the need for early identification of problematic behaviors to provide appropriate remedies, ensuring that learners achieve their full potential.

Based on these conclusions, several recommendations were made. Interventions should address negative behaviors, such as conflicts and interruptions, through counseling and conflict resolution programs. Positive behaviors should be reinforced, and strategies to enhance engagement and support for struggling students should be implemented. Additional support should be provided to students with below-satisfactory performance, and tailored approaches should be considered for male and female students based on identified differences. Continuous monitoring and evaluation of behavior and academic performance are essential for adjusting educational strategies, and professional development for teachers should focus on managing behaviors and fostering positive relationships to create a supportive learning environment.

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